

Deliverable 7.3
Communications
Dissemination and
Sustainability
Interim Report.

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Details

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01

Introduction

Introduction

This Communications Dissemination and Sustainability Interim Report (D7.3) reviews the dissemination activities of the Accelerate Future HEI Horizon Europe project for the first 30 months of operation from January 2023 to June 2025 as outlined within the original application and Communication, Dissemination and Sustainability plan (D7.1) and builds on the initial report (D7.2) delivered in December 2023.

It includes a summary of the main activities as well as a short overview of the dissemination strategy used, based on the Communication, Dissemination and Sustainability plan. It highlights the project targets, the stakeholders and the target audience. It then goes on to report on the key performance indicators from the project against the targets including a performance review of the three social media channels used: LinkedIn, Bluesky and X as well as including performance metrics from the project’s dedicated website.

It outlines the dissemination plans for the project over the next 12 months of the project. Partner content is included as part of the dissemination reporting and examples are highlighted to show where success has been achieved.

Deliverables		Due Date
D7.1	Initial Communication Dissemination & Sustainability Plan	M6
D7.2	Updated Communication Dissemination & Sustainability Plan & Initial Report	M12
D7.3	Interim Communication Dissemination & Sustainability Report	M30
D7.4	Final Interim Communication Dissemination & Sustainability Report	M48

Refresher: What is a Communication, Dissemination and Sustainability Plan?

The overall objectives of the WP7 Communications, Dissemination and Sustainability Plan are:

- To **create awareness and understanding** of the importance of Entrepreneurial and Innovative Universities.
- To **raise awareness** about acceleration services and methodologies.
- **Support the integration** of all stakeholders in the different phases of the project.
- **Widely disseminate** the project results and outputs.
- **Set the foundation** for further implementation/exploitation of the results of the project.

We understand **Communication, Dissemination and Sustainability** as follows;

Stakeholders and Target Groups

Promotion and awareness-raising is an important part of the communications and dissemination process. It is key the project is delivered to its primary target audiences. Target audiences are engaged with messages that will be specifically tailored to them via the project's multiple channels.

The **Accelerate Future HEI** project includes primary target groups and stakeholders of influence who participate in and benefit from the project. To generate and exploit the maximum value of the project, the Communications, Dissemination and Sustainability Plan is responsive to the needs of our key target groups and focuses on the respective channels, and multipliers to reach the target groups, the material and messages delivered, as well as the type and frequency of the communication intended.

The project methodology and underlying processes predefine the development of open-access methodologies and a showcase of results. With these open-access deliverables, we are creating a direct impact on the stakeholder groups outside of the testing HEI partners.

CORE TARGET GROUPS

- HEI Testing Partners
 - HEI Leadership
- Non-academic/Professional Staff
- Academic Staff/Lecturers/Researchers
 - Students & Life-Long Learners

EXTERNAL STAKEHOLDERS

- Other HEIs (national, regional, local and European levels)
 - Industrial partners, SMEs and startups
- Public bodies (Local, regional, national and European), including municipalities, departments of education, governmental support offices for higher education/entrepreneurship/regional development, etc. Network organisations (local, regional, national and European), entrepreneurship and innovation ecosystem drivers, Policy makers, policy advocates and thought leaders

Targets and Measuring Impact

Central to the project Communications, Dissemination and Sustainability Plan is communicating the project's benefits and outcomes and ensuring engagement with the key target groups and regional, national and international stakeholders for a long-lasting impact of the project.

The project's Communications, Dissemination and Sustainability plan's success is measured against the following criteria for final evaluation:

- Proper use of communication channels and materials to reach the end user and target groups.
- Whether the target audiences were reached and engaged
- To what extent are the project's results known and used outside the project consortium
- How users and stakeholders judge the value of outputs.
- What impact are outputs having upon the practice and understanding of target audiences, and what are the prospects for further impact in the future?
- To what extent has sustainability been secured, and external recognition achieved?

02 Summary

Summary

Accelerate Future HEI has reached the halfway point of implementing its robust Communication, Dissemination and Sustainability Plan. The planned activities have been successful in reaching and engaging the target audiences thus far. This interim report shows that the first stage of activities to raise awareness has been reinforced by building upon a strong brand, promotional materials and a dedicated website.

As part of the second in-person meeting (Year 1), MMS conducted a Communications Workshop with the nine HEI testing partners to discuss the dissemination activities they conducted, the communication channels and methods they found to be most effective to reach the target audience. Finally, what learnings did they gain to inform dissemination activities for Year 2? From these learnings, the partners increased the project’s reach through their institutional communication channels and proactive outreach via various multimedia to further embed the entrepreneurial culture within and beyond participating institutions for widespread influence. Flyers specifically designed to support training activities were used to support capacity building and knowledge exchange.

Our project website traffic has more than doubled its number of unique visitors to 43,554 while our three social media channels have also increased their following (1009). The additional channel of Bluesky was added in 2024 following a decrease in followers on X. We have shared and promoted our first deliverables since 2024, created and shared two ezines, securing 666 downloads and doubled our number of blog posts (36). The addition of short-form video content offered variety both on the website and in social media postings.

Blog posts	Unique Website Visitors	Social Media Posts	Impressions
36	43,554	987	48,286

The project partnership has been successful in raising awareness amongst our target audience through their activities. This has been shown in the significant number of social media posts (221) and related impressions (691,039). Partners have been actively hosting and attending events both locally and internationally to raise our project’s profile and directly connect with our target audiences. We will continue to encourage partners to fully exploit their activities via their institutional channels to maximise reach and engagement.

Blog posts	LinkedIn	X	Bluesky	Partner Website	Other	Social Media Posts	Impressions	Direct Distribution via email	Local events/workshops	International Events
31	115	136	85	29	46	221	691,039	6	21	22

Summary

Promotional goods designed by Momentum have increased the brand's visibility on campuses, at events and meetings. They have created a positive response from partners and their Institutional Transformation Acceleration Project (ITAP) teams, who have requested further items. Accelerate Future HEI has continued to collaborate with the two sister projects, aUPaEU and CATALISI, as part of a communications alliance. They have achieved several cross-promotional activities under a shared brand in a cohesive manner through regular monthly meetings and open communication. Together, they will work with the Horizon Results Booster support service for dissemination and exploitation activities to reinforce their efforts.

Over the next 12 months, through the rollout of the M30 deliverables and the continued development of each partner's ITAP, the partners and stakeholders will actively share their progress and results to bolster our dissemination and communications activities. A further two ezines and continued blog posting will work to maintain and increase web traffic and social media impressions.

To encourage partners to contribute content, we regularly highlight partner success stories on our website. At partner meetings, metrics are shared regularly to show progress and recognition for partners who have contributed. The key focus for the next year will be for HEIs to show their transformation via a video and infographic series, which will offer further multimedia strategies to engage our target audiences. We will seek to include testimonials, results, or lessons learned from the partners, their ITAP teams and stakeholders to sustain and validate impact.

03

Key Activities & Targets

Overview: Delivered to date

This report details the communication and dissemination activities achieved to date. These include the project brand design, the website and associated materials, social media activities, promotional materials, as well as our communications alliance. Below is

- 1) Website launched, supported by press releases for partners to use across all channels.
- 2) Website monthly updates by Momentum to include news, new documents to be made available for download, information on events, etc., at each monthly meeting.
- 3) Image bank created - Collected and provided access to license-free images to reflect the specific target groups.
- 4) Momentum created a specific Social Media Content Kit for the social media channels.
- 5) Partners contributed to profiling their Reach Database, developing content and recording their dissemination activities every quarter.
- 6) All partners contributed to the development and update of the project website, ezines, blog and news section, multimedia material highlighting the developments within the scope of the project in their region. Partners can translate the content for dissemination for national purposes.
- 7) Each partner displays news about the project on their respective official websites and includes the news about the project and the project's developments in their newsletters to reach their regional stakeholders.

Project Brand

To raise awareness amongst HEI internal and external stakeholders about the importance of an entrepreneurial approach inside and outside of the university.

Building Awareness was the first phase of our approach as we sought to build up an engaged community around Accelerate Future HEI.

Brand Building

Momentum created a strong professional and engaging project brand and intent tagline. This was the first step in the visibility creation of the project under our Communication ambition. The brand is also available in an animated format, as presented on the project website: <https://acceleratefuturehei.eu/>

Key brand features include: -

- Text-based brands are known to lead to brand longevity. The brand emphasises the word accelerate, and the future-focused project ambition by using an upward forward-facing arrow design.
- The colour combination of red and black balances positive energy balanced with intent. The primary colour red gives positive energy while black adds certainty and authority.
- Our brand is leading out on a series of design templates and promotional materials (flyers, logos, signs and banners).
- Our brand guidelines will be used by project partners to ensure brand consistency across: -
 - Brand and brand usage
 - Colour specifications
 - Typography
 - Use of trademark symbols

Promotional Materials

We have built further on the marketing collateral created at the start of the project, which includes a series of marketing tools that allowed us to reach large audiences in a short period. Specific flyers for training and events are created on an ad hoc basis. All content can be found at this link for the duration of the project: [WP7](#)

- Brand Manual & logo
- 1-page project summary.
- 5 slides project presentation, in editable PowerPoint format and created as an introductory video
- Project brochure (awareness building theme) * to illustrate key project concepts using infographics and visual aids. The project brochure will be uploaded in electronic PDF format onto the project website as from its production and it will be easy to download and share.
- Infographics summarising the project results as are striving for – Our Ambition at a Glance
- Project roll-up banner
- Project e-zine template.
- Project reports template.
- Event-specific project flyers, for various events
- Online banners including branded social media headers, placeholders etc. *
- Graphics to support partner dissemination e.g., our badge of honour

Example flyers created

accelerate future HEI
supporting future focused higher education

It is an exciting and important time to focus on the future potential of Higher Education Institutions (HEIs)

About Accelerate Future HEI

HEIs can positively impact regional and Europe-wide social and economic development through education, research and engagement. However, they require targeted support to enhance their capability to fully realise their potential.

Accelerate Future HEI will develop and test acceleration services, to equip HEIs with the skills and capacity to drive institutional transformation towards becoming more entrepreneurial and innovative institutions over the next four years

KEY OBJECTIVES

- TO IDENTIFY** the status quo of the HEI and its ecosystem regarding entrepreneurial and innovative activities.
- TO DEVELOP** test and implement acceleration services that help institutions undertake a transformation roadmap and projects.
- TO BUILD** the capacity of the participating HEIs staff to implement the transformation roadmaps through a skills development program.
- TO EVALUATE** the strategies from HEIs supervised by an 'acceleration board' of independent experts.
- TO GENERATE** policy feedback to the European Commission as well as provide widespread dissemination of the pilot results to other target groups.

To Learn more visit the project www.acceleratefuturehei.eu

accelerate future HEI
supporting future focused higher education

IMPACTFUL RESEARCHERS

2 Oct - 5 Nov 2025

This dynamic online training program, delivered through **six interactive workshops over six weeks**, brings together ambitious researchers from all parts of the world, across all disciplines and at every career stage, who are looking to use their research to create impact. Led by global experts and providing best practices.

You will be taken through a series of interactive workshops, seminars and discussions to broaden the impact of your work, embed impact at all stages of your research initiatives and establish your profile as an impactful researcher.

This program consists of six workshops:

- 01 Setting up for Impactful Research
- 02 Impact Mindset
- 03 Communicating Research and its Impact
- 04 Creating a Personal Brand
- 05 Setting up for External Engagement Success
- 06 Valorisation Pathways

Who should attend? This training is ideal for academics and researchers at all career stages and from any discipline who are eager to amplify the impact of their work, secure more funding, and make meaningful contributions to society. If you're ready to think beyond traditional research outputs and learn how to create real-world impact, this is for you! Open to Accelerate Future HEI partner universities.

Project Website

The project website is performing very well <https://acceleratefuturehei.eu/> resulting in 43,554 unique visitors since its inception in 2023. It reflects our corporate design and is the central access point for the project. All data generated during the course of the project is made available through a project website, which is continuously updated.

The project website works to raise awareness and share information about the project and will be kept active for at least 3 years after the completion of the project.

The main features of the website are: -

- A dynamic and engaging landing page and a selection of subpages highlighting the main information about the project and contact details of the partners.
- Mobile-friendly design
- Use of best practice web development, SEO optimisation, integration with different media formats, e.g., infographics, videos, and presentations to create a dynamic intuitive environment for all visitors.
- Incorporation of resources repository with all materials and outputs of the project in an easily downloadable format.
- Source of downloadable marketing materials (e.g., posters, flyers) to equip all stakeholders to promote the project outcomes and both training programmes and toolkits.
- We publish annual e-zines available for free download. Two are available now and four issues will be published in total during the project lifetime.
- Publishing articles about the main project outputs, content and promotion of the training programmes, and project events will occur on the project website.
- All WP deliverables will be available for download and form the basis of dissemination activity via shorter engaging articles and posts.

Download Our Brochure

Join us on the journey of HEI transformation and innovation to discover how **Accelerate Future HEI** will develop and test acceleration services, to equip HEIs with the skills and capacity to support and drive institutional change.

[Download Brochure](#)

An information brochure was designed for download from the website to keep the target group and the general public informed about the objectives, the project activities, the participants in the project, and the main expected results.

1,398 downloads

43,554: No. of Unique website visitors since it's inception 21st December 2023

COUNTRY

- United States
- Netherlands
- Ireland
- Portugal
- Austria
- China
- Finland

The majority of traffic is from the US, Portugal, Ireland and Spain. The website hosts blog post news items (#36) including a project video and brochure.

Source: Google Analytics

Main Project Deliverables

Following project officer approval, all deliverables before M30 were made available for public dissemination on the project website. These deliverables are clearly shown as interactive hotspots on an illustration for free download. The corresponding download figures demonstrate that these deliverables have been enthusiastically received and utilised. The HEI Strategic Vision Statements (D2.1) have achieved the most downloads to date at 616 times, followed by the project’s Data Management Plan (D1.1) with 479 times.: [Results - Accelerate Future HEI](#)

Downloads per Deliverable

D1.1: 479	D3.2: 158
D1.2: 147	D5.1: 194
D2.1: 616	D6.1: 217
D2.2: 227	D7.1: 134
D3.1: 233	D7.2: 229

Multimedia Content

We prioritise digital media content and approaches. Momentum created a short promotional video introducing the project, our partnership, and our activities. It has secured 75 views. Additional promotional videos and short-form video content have been produced with partners, resulting in 11 videos housed in a video library on the project website and resulting in 227 views. [Video Library - Accelerate Future HEI](#) These videos have been posted on the project's social media channels to maximise visibility and vary the type of content used.

Accelerate Future HEI - Supporting Future Focused Higher Education

[View the AFH video here: Accelerate Future HEI - Supporting Future Focused Higher Education \(youtube.com\)](#)

Welcome to our Accelerate Future HEI video library. Hear directly from the project partners about their experiences and reflections. Start watching now to expand your knowledge and become inspired to join our mission to support transformation in higher education.

Accelerate Future HEI: Reflections On Year Two
from project co-ordinator, Rimanto Rusaito

Dr. Sarah Jabbar: An Overview of Accelerate Future HEI

Dr. Emese Prihoda - MATE: A Multi-Campus University

Kathrin Albrocht - WP 6 Leaders: Monitoring & Evaluation

Samantha Carty - WP7 Leaders: Communication, Dissemination & Sustainability

Pedro Amaral: A Stakeholder's Impression

Inés Flores Colan: Plans For The Year Ahead

Dr. Diana Andong: Supporting Digital Transformation

Universidad Europea de Canarias (UEC): Working With Our University Stakeholders

Title: Strategic: Vision of Universidad Europea de Canarias (UEC)

Accelerate Future HEI:
Reflections On Year One

[Video Library - Accelerate Future HEI](#)

Ezines

The creation of two ezines in the **Accelerate Future HEI Ezine Series** [Ezines - Accelerate Future HEI](#) has stimulated desire amongst our target groups to participate in the activities that lead to a more entrepreneurial culture within and outside the nine participating universities. Each partner is tasked with sharing the publications with their networks.

For the ezines, we created a bespoke branded ezine template, and all partners create and contribute content according to a content plan. The topics selected for inclusion in the ezine introduce the scope and aim of the project, introduce some of the partners, outline our work to date and report on each work package as well as updates from our two Horizon Europe sister projects.

The ezines are circulated directly and are available for download in PDF format with open access. To support the distribution of the ezines, we have designed a dedicated space on the project website where all ezines are hosted and available to download. We have also set up a GDPR-compliant integrated email subscription facility on the website to create a project-specific database. Invitations to subscribe are scheduled for social media promotion regularly throughout the project's lifetime. Each ezine launch is promoted on the project's social media channels and with a blog post on the website.

The ezine series is circulated widely via partner newsletters and channels, project subscribers' updates, project social media, and the project website, as well as on external resource/news-sharing platforms. While partners and their networks are the core disseminators, we also invite partners to suggest additional platforms.

Ezine 1: March 2024, 452 downloads

Ezine 2: March 2025, 214 downloads

Blogposts

Partners continue to proactively submit regular blog posts to the project website and also follow a blog posting schedule – Appendix 2. We have used the blog posts to update the project stakeholders about the ‘entrepreneurial university journey’ featuring partner profiles, institution events and project workshops and meetings. Momentum works closely with the two Horizon Europe sister projects to cross-promote their events and activities. MMS, in collaboration with partners, seek opportunities to engage with the target audience and build awareness through these activities.

A sample of the 36 blog posts available on the project website: [News - Accelerate Future HEI](#)

<p>Driving regional innovation and entrepreneurship</p> <p>By Iveta Putriņa, Mg.paed., and Aglita Smitha, Dr. sc.admin., Vidzeme University of Applied Sciences. Universities in regions, although small, play a huge role in the</p> <p>READ MORE »</p> <p>April 3, 2025</p>		
<p>Striking a Balance Between Innovation and Responsibility</p> <p>By Aglita Smitha, Dr.sc.admin., VIA in today's fast-paced technological world, the ethics surrounding technology have become a growing and intricate concern. As innovation continues to</p> <p>READ MORE »</p> <p>January 6, 2025</p>		
<p>Embracing the Future: UCLL's Strategy Day</p> <p>By Katrien Vandael and Lotte Owaere, UCLL. In November, the atmosphere at UCLL, University of Applied Sciences, was charged with anticipation and excitement as the</p> <p>READ MORE »</p> <p>November 20, 2024</p>		

Social Media

Three dedicated social media platforms (X, LinkedIn and Bluesky) are kept active weekly by posting news about the project and sharing the news from external news channels within the thematic scope of the project to build awareness with stakeholders. In 2024, following an unexplained reduction in the number of followers on the X platform, the partnership established a BlueSky account to diversify our channels. Partners assist with target audience recruitment and with identifying social media accounts to engage with. Project partners are included in social media posting, including associated alliances @incore_eu @eudres_alliance @REA_research [@HorizonEU](#)

LinkedIn: [Accelerate Future HEI: Overview | LinkedIn](#)

X: [AccelerateFutureHEI \(@AccFutureHEI\) / Twitter](#)

Bluesky: [Accelerate Future HEI \(@accfuturehei.bsky.social\) — Bluesky](#)

We use the following hashtags in social media posts to help amplify our messaging:

- #AccFutureHEI
- #HorizonEU
- #highereducationinnovation
- #REA (research executive agency)

As part of the social media strategy, we ensure project partners are steered towards a unified approach to strategic social media sharing and tagging in their expansive networks that will contribute to building our project visibility. To achieve this, a detailed professional **‘Social Media Content Kit’** was shared with the partners that informed them about the key target groups (including their specific interests and values), type of content (short and long copy), frequency of posting and key hashtags, design, style, and length of the language to be used for each of the social media channels.

Social media links are provided from the main page of the project website to keep visitors updated with real-time information and the opportunity to share and reshare the latest developments of the project. Calls to action to follow the Accelerate Future HEI social media accounts are published on the project brochures and flyers. Social media is designed for conversation, not for announcements. To be effective, we have committed to regularly posting across our channels and engaging in topic-based contributions as appropriate. We encourage everyone involved in the project to join in the conversation so that multiple points of view are reflected.

The large number of followers (1,009) across the three social media channels, X, Bluesky and LinkedIn, demonstrate a wide reach and positive engagement. While X followers have remained static, LinkedIn and Bluesky are growing steadily with regular engagement via likes, comments and reposting of content. Project partners use their institution’s social media channels to supplement the project activities.

X/Twitter (as of June 2025)

- **535 Tweets**
- **85 Followers**

A sample of recently posted content

AccelerateFutureHEI @AccFutureHEI · Jan 20

After careful consideration, we have decided to discontinue using X for Accelerate Future HEI.

While X has been a valuable platform for engaging with our audience, recent changes and challenges have made it less suitable for achieving our goals.

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0 1 1 1 49

AccelerateFutureHEI @AccFutureHEI · Jan 20

Moving forward, we'll be focusing on LinkedIn as our primary platform to share our updates, insights, and stories.

Thank you for supporting us - be sure to follow us on LinkedIn to stay up to date with our work.

Follow us here: [linkedin.com/company/acceleratefuturehei/](https://www.linkedin.com/company/acceleratefuturehei/)

2/2

linkedin.com

Accelerate Future HEI | LinkedIn

Accelerate Future HEI | 896 followers on LinkedIn. Supporting future-focused higher education ...

0 1 1 1 14

AccelerateFutureHEI @AccFutureHEI · Jan 13

We are delighted to showcase the Strategic Vision Statement from Magyar Agrár- és Élettudományi Egyetem (MATE), the Hungarian University of Agriculture and Life Sciences.

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**Strategic Vision Statement:
Magyar Agrár- és Élettudományi
Egyetem (MATE)**

MATE
accelerate future HEI

0 1 1 1 36

[Show more replies](#)

AccelerateFutureHEI @AccFutureHEI · Jan 8

Wrapping up 2024 with our Project Coordinators reflecting on an incredible year and looking ahead to 2025 plans. Watch our highlights! Accelerate Future HEI Year 2 Projections

@aupaeu @catalisi and @accelerate future HEI

1/2

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AccelerateFutureHEI @AccFutureHEI · Jan 8

Jesus Alcober, Rimante Rusaite ,Laura Mentini Stefania Laneve

[youtube.com/watch?v=q5TA-5...](https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=q5TA-5...)

2/2

youtube.com

Accelerate Future HEI Year 2 Projections

As we end 2024 and venture into 2025, the Accelerate Future HEI, aUPaEU and Catalisi ...

0 1 1 1 6

AccelerateFutureHEI @AccFutureHEI · Jan 6

We're delighted to introduce the Board of Experts for @AccFutureHEI , a Horizon Europe-funded initiative focused on transforming higher education institutions through innovation and entrepreneurship.

1/4

0 1 1 4 3 227

AccelerateFutureHEI @AccFutureHEI · Dec 30, 2024

Our next e-zine is coming out soon, and we can't wait to share it with you! We're reflecting on the highlights of an incredible year and our acceleration plans for the year ahead

Join our growing community

Subscribe to our newsletter here: acceleratefuturehei.eu/contact/

1/2

**Sign up for Our
NEWSLETTER**

0 1 1 1 21

AccelerateFutureHEI @AccFutureHEI · Dec 18, 2024

On November 4th, @stetnico marked a new chapter in doctoral education with the launch of the Técnico Doctoral School at the 10th edition of their PhD Open Days.

1/5

NEW BLOG POST

**Reshaping the training of
Técnico's PhD students**

0 1 1 1 27

AccelerateFutureHEI @AccFutureHEI · Dec 16, 2024

Today, an entrepreneurial and innovative approach is essential for all universities. This is where our Communication, Dissemination, and Sustainability Plan in WP 7 plays an important role.

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**Communication, Dissemination and
Sustainability Plan**

01

Communication

02

Dissemination

03

Sustainability

accelerate future HEI

0 1 1 2 1 52

AccelerateFutureHEI @AccFutureHEI · Dec 11, 2024

From September 17 to 21, 2024, ESIRUI, the engineering school of the @Univ_Reunion, hosted its Design Sprint as part of France Design Week.

The event brought together forty third-year students to deal with a key innovation challenge: waste management.

1/4

NEW BLOG POST

**First Design Sprint at
University of La Réunion**

0 1 1 2 1 112

AccelerateFutureHEI @AccFutureHEI · Dec 9, 2024

The ADKAR model is a powerful change management methodology that focuses on guiding individuals and groups through the five stages of change. Each stage is important for ensuring that the change process is understood, accepted, and effectively implemented.

1/3

**5 BENEFITS
of the ADKAR Model**

1

1

Raise overall awareness and generate interest in the mission of Accelerate Future HEI.

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LinkedIn (as of June 2025)

- **904 Followers**
- **2,683 Reactions**
- **45 Comments**
- **195 Shares**
- **3004 Page Views**
- **1431 Unique Visitors**
- **75 Custom Button Clicks**

A sample of recently posted content

Accelerate Future HEI
901 followers
1h · 🌐

Have you downloaded our e-zines yet?

They're packed with insights and progress from across the Accelerate Future HEI project.

E-zine 1 shows where it all began, the early steps, and how our vision took shape. Workshops, best practices, and partner stories reveal how HEIs are rethinking their role.

E-zine 2 takes us to the halfway mark, with partners piloting Acceleration Services, refining strategies and building capacity to achieve their Institutional Transformation Action Projects (ITAPs).

Download both here: https://lnkd.in/d_VKYpbU

Accelerate Future HEI
901 followers
6d · 🌐

What have we achieved that wouldn't have been possible without Accelerate Future HEI?

New ideas, new teams, new confidence. Working together is making things better for higher education.

Swipe through to see what our partners said when asked: " What have you been able to achieve that wouldn't have been possible without the project?"

Download the e-zine and see what our partners have achieved so far: <https://lnkd.in/dbij8-tw>

Bluesky (as of June 2025)

- **20 Followers**
- **86 Reactions**
- **6 Comments**
- **7 Shares**
- **131 Page Views**
- **94 Unique Visitors**
- **13 Custom Button Clicks**

A sample of recently posted content

Storytelling

Over the next 12 months, a series of nine short videos highlighting the reach of acceleration services towards Entrepreneurial and Innovative Universities in Europe (one per testing partner) will be created to showcase the transformations implemented.

To kick start this process, MMS held a storytelling workshop at the January 2025 partner meeting and, using a storytelling template, set each partner the task of storyboarding their video. This workshop aimed to equip partners with the necessary tools to effectively communicate and disseminate their ITAP outcomes. Since the workshop, each HEI has developed an idea and script for their video and is starting to capture relevant content that can be used in the final output. These videos will be hosted on the project website and promoted on social media, together with specially designed infographics.

Branded Merchandise

In 2024, Momentum designed and distributed promotional hoodies and t-shirts to all project partners. This initiative served multiple valuable strategic purposes:

- * Enhancing team morale
- * Generating enthusiasm around the project
- * Increasing brand visibility, particularly among internal HEI stakeholders
- * Creating goodwill among partners
- * Supporting promotional and media opportunities
- * Cohesive visuals for partner meetings and photo documentation

The positive response to this initiative inspired UEC, the host of the subsequent partner meeting in Tenerife, to develop and distribute their own branded items, further promoting the project and strengthening partner engagement. In January 2025, a second batch of branded apparel was produced and distributed. This included customised allocations for each partner as well as the full membership of the Accelerate Future HEI Board of Experts.

Scientific Publications & Other Channels

There is a strong opportunity for partners to utilise scientific publications as part of their dissemination activities. Many of the participating University team members are researchers for whom international scientific publications are an important part of their work and career. A large amount of data has already been obtained, which can be analysed from a scientific point of view, interpreted and shared via academic research publications. In addition, the publications also give prestige to the participating Universities, as well as help to spread the results of the project more widely. Publication in internationally recognised and prestigious journals can bolster dissemination efforts and bring the project findings to our target audience. Two universities are currently working on papers that they plan to publish in H2 2025. In addition to regular internal events, partners have been very active in participating in workshops, events and conferences representing Accelerate Future HEI.

E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-Novators Science Policy Conference

UIIN Conference 2025, Amsterdam.

Our Communications Alliance

Accelerate Future HEI has formed a productive communications alliance with two sister projects under the same call of the European Research Area: aUPaEU and CATALISI. Our projects share the same values and objectives to improve Higher Education Institutions, accelerating their institutional transformation. We have been actively collaborating on communication and dissemination activities. We conduct monthly meetings to coordinate activities under our shared brand: Together for HEI transformation.

Our joint activities include:

- Monthly communication meetings
- Joint social media campaigns
- Shared branding development
- Shared event spreadsheet for synergic participation
- Joint policy deliverables
- INORMS Congress joint submission

On a practical level, we created a common SharePoint folder to document our communication activities which to date include, joint social media campaigns (3) joint blog posts (2); reciprocal features in each project’s website and newsletters (3); shared online Zenodo community; continuous identification of events to jointly participate. We have recently taken a step further and in early 2025, we engaged with the European Commission initiative, the [Horizon Booster Platform](#) service, to discuss the possibility of all three sister projects using their free services to support the work we’re doing in dissemination and exploitation. So far, we have each completed our readiness assessment to create a roadmap for personalised support for our projects. Looking ahead, we aim to use this free service to increase our knowledge and awareness of activities that will benefit Accelerate Future HEI and its partners.

As the projects progress, we will individually and collectively look at other platforms on which to share our results look to share its results such as: [Open Research Europe platform](#), [CORDIScovery podcasts](#), [Research & innovation success stories](#), [Horizon Magazine](#), [R&I Days](#).

04

Appendices

Partner Dissemination

To realise and reinforce the overall dissemination of the Accelerate Future HEI project, as dissemination lead Momentum

- Includes the feedback of all partners on its dissemination activities
- Welcomes all feedback and input from partners in the creation and sharing of promotional materials.
- Requires all partners to register their activities in a communication reporting document and share it with Momentum every 6 months. All partners save evidence of their activities to assess if actions are being carried out and to see what activities had the biggest impact on the stakeholders.

Any feedback and partner reporting were considered for inclusion in the Dissemination Partner updates. All Appendices are completed by partners and kept on the SharePoint link for continuous reference and review.

The Dissemination Record shows the dissemination activities of all partners, providing an overview of the various kinds of dissemination activities, a description, dates when the activity took place, location, dissemination level, target group, number of people reached and the proof of the activity: [Appendix 4- Partner Dissemination Record.xlsx](#)

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